

THE DISTRIBUTION AND THE DIFFUSION OF Si ABOVE THE LIQUIDUS IN SiCp/Al COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: The properties and the structures of liquid melt above liquidus play an important role in determining the resultant properties of the alloy and the composite, the distribution and the diffusion of Si above liquidus in molten composite melt are responsible for the interfacial reaction between SiC reinforcement and molten aluminium above liquidus. In this paper, the melt structures of SiCp/Al composites with two different reinforcement volume fraction were investigated using Liquid Metal X-Ray Diffraction and Differential Scanning Calorimetry. The experimental results showed that the melt structures of SiCp/Al composite are different from that of liquid matrix alloy, Si-Si hump in the pair radial distribution function in SiCp/Al composite melt and the DSC trace indicated that Si is non-well-distributed above liquidus, the size change of short-range-order(SRO) in SiCp/Al composite melt indicated the diffusion of Si released from chemical reaction between SiC and molten Al is possible only after a given temperature or after some extent concentration fluctuation of Si. The existence of Si-Si hump and the size change of SRO are attributed to the chemical reaction in SiCp/Al composite and the existence of reinforcing particles, high volume fraction plays more greater influence on the Si-Si hump and the size change of SRO than low volume fraction.

KEYWORDS: Melt structure, Distribution and Diffusion of Si, Interfacial Reaction, SiC/Al Composite

INTRODUCTION

A large and increasing proportion of discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites (DRMMCs) are presently produced by solidification processing, in which the metal matrix is molten before it is combined with the particles, whiskers, or fibers that are to serve as its reinforcing phase in the final composite material. Due to the existence of reinforcing particles, fluid flow, mass and heat transfer, chemical reaction take place in the composite material before it is fully solidified, thus the solidification processing of metal matrix composite is different from that of matrix alloy. The properties and the structures of liquid melt above liquidus play an important role in determining the resultant properties of the alloy and the composite. Recently, the research on the structures and the properties of the liquid are being paid more attentions and some great progress have been made[1,2].

SiCp/Al composites is one of the most important DRMMCs and it is now established that SiC react with molten aluminum, producing Al_4C_3 and silicon, according to the following reaction

Silicon formed in this reaction dissolves in unreacted aluminum, giving rise to an Al-Si liquid alloy[3-5]. The melt structures and the distribution and diffusion of silicon is responsible for the further reaction between SiC and molten aluminum above liquidus, and the knowledge of melt structure, especially the local melt structure around the reinforcement is more important, since it may control the following stage of the interface reaction zone, and thereby affect the final microstructures and properties of the interface. But unfortunately, no studies have been carried out on the melt structures of composites above liquidus until now. In this paper, the melt structures of SiCp/Al composites above liquidus were investigated for the first time, by means of Liquid Metal X-Ray Diffraction (LMXRD) and Differential Scanning Calorimeter(DSC) in order to provide basic profiles of melt structure in SiCp/Al composites above liquidus.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Composite Fabrication

SiCp/pure Al composites used were fabricated using vacuum-high pressure infiltration processing. The dominant phase of SiCp used as the reinforcement was α -SiC(6H) and the average size SiCp was $7\mu m$ about. Two types of SiCp/Al composite(10 and 40Vol%SiC) were used to vary the melt structure characteristics during the remelting.

Liquid Metal x-ray Diffraction

Diffraction was carried out using $\theta - \theta$ type liquid metal x-ray diffractionmeter in Ukraine academy of science. Fig.1 showed the schematic illustration of the Liquid Metal X-Ray Diffraction for SiCp/Al composites. $MoK\alpha$ radiation, is reflected from the free surface of the specimen, reaches the detector through a graphite monochromator in the diffraction beam. High temperature x-ray diffractions were carried out in high purity helium atmosphere of 1.3×10^5 pa before the chamber cleaned in vacuum of 2×10^{-6} pa. Specimen were placed in a alumina crucible of $30 \times 25 \times 8$ mm in size, using Ta sheet as heating element, and surface of the specimen was fit to one horizontal position using laser calibrator. Some other parameters used in this experiment included: scanning voltage was 40 Kv, current was 30mA, exposition time is 30 s, measured angle 2θ was from 5~90 Degree. The experimental temperature for pure Al and SiCp/Al composites are 675 °C, 775 °C, 875 °C, 1075 °C, respectively.

Data Processing for Liquid Structure

The information about the structure of composite melt was obtained after the solid phase information was filtered from the diffraction intensity profiles[6]. The outline of the data processing for liquid melt is as the follows:

The scattering intensity measured in arbitrary unit can be converted into the coherent scattering intensity per atom in an electron unit I_a^{coh} , using the generalized Krogh-Moe-Norman method. Multiple scanning, resulting in an accumulation of more than 3×10^4 counts per angle, reducing the total estimate of error for the structure factor $S(Q)$, to less than $\pm 2\%$. The total structure factor can be written as

$$S(Q) = \frac{I_a^{coh}}{\langle f^2(Q) \rangle} = c_1 k_1^2 S_{11}(Q) + c_2 k_2^2 S_{22}(Q) + 2(c_1 c_2)^{\frac{1}{2}} k_1 k_2 S_{12}(Q) \quad (2)$$

Pair distribution function $g(r)$ was Fourier transformation of the structure factor $S(Q)$:

$$g(r) = 1 + \frac{1}{2\pi^2 \rho_0 r} \int_0^\infty Q [S(Q) - 1] \sin(Qr) dQ \quad (3)$$

where Q is the scattering vector, $Q = \frac{4\pi \sin(\theta)}{\lambda}$, 2θ is the scattering angle, λ is the wavelength of diffraction beam, $c_i = N_i / N$, and c_i, N_i are concentration and number of the atom type i in the melt, N is the total number in the scattering volume, $k_i = \frac{f_i}{[f^2(Q)]^{\frac{1}{2}}}$,

$[f^2(Q)] = \sum_i c_i f_i^2$ f_i is the atomic scattering factor of atom type i , in addition, ρ_0 and r , the average number density of atoms and the distance from the reference atom, respectively. The size of short-range-order (SRO) in the liquid melt $r_c = g(\pm 1.02)$, representing the lower limit of the atom cluster [6].

Fig.1 Schematic illustration of the Liquid Metal X-Ray Diffraction

Calorimetric Measurements

The composite samples after the thermal history in liquid metal X-ray diffraction were remelted in a high purity alumina pan in Netsch DSC404 instrument runs were carried out at a heating rate 20 °C/min from ambient to 850 °C, subsequently cooling to ambient temperature at 20 °C/min, and under dynamic high purity argon atmosphere(80 ml/min). High purity corundum was used as a reference, and all DSC thermogram were normalized to the actual amount of metal (in percentage of weight) in each composites.

RESULTS

The temperature variation of the pair distribution function $g(r)$ of melt are given in Figs.2 ~4 using the results of molten pure Al and SiCp/Al composite with 10vol% and 40vol% reinforcement volume. Even though the data for the liquid Al and the SiCp/Al composite melt measured at the same temperature, some differences are still demonstrated in the pair distribution function $g(r)$. As shown in Fig.2, the melt of pure Al produce a very similar Pair Distribution Function $g(r)$ at different temperature. All the results for the liquid Al show a

relatively sharp first peak and subsequent small peaks on the high Q region. This implies that the fundamental feature in atomic distribution for a liquid melt are approximately more or less by a random mixture. But the structure of SiCp/Al melt, as shown in Figs.3 ~4, is different from that of liquid pure Al, with the temperature increasing, the first peak of the $g(r)$ curve becomes broader and more asymmetric, and the $g(r)$ is also characterized by splitting of the second main peaks into a large peak and two small one, implying the non-well distributed of the melt.

It is immediately evident from Figs.3~4 that a small Si-Si hump in the first main peak of $g(r)$ was observed, with increasing the temperature. For 10Vol% SiCp/Al composite melt, the hump peak was progressively emerging when holding at 875 °C, while it is very clear when 1075 °C; For 40vol%SiCp/Al composite melt, the hump peak always exist in the first main peak of the $g(r)$ above 775 °C, the position of this hump is 3.20 Å or so.

Fig.5 showed the temperature dependence of the size of short-range-order(SRO) in liquid Al and the two kinds of SiCp/Al composite melt, the size of SRO r_c in liquid Al is lowing with the temperature increasing, implying that the fundamental features in the atomic distribution for the liquid are approximated more or less by a random mixture, whereas the size of SRO in SiCp/Al composite melt are lowing only above a given temperature, while it is more or less a constant, also indicating the melt structure in SiCp/Al are different from that in liquid Al.

Fig.2 Temperature dependence of the pair distribution function $g(r)$ for pure Al

Fig.3 Temperature dependence of the pair distribution function $g(r)$ for 10% SiC/Al melt

Fig.4 Temperature dependence of the pair distribution function $g(r)$ for 40% SiC/Al melt

Fig.5 Temperature dependence of cluster size in liquid Al and SiCp/Al melt

DISCUSSION

The Distribution of Si From the Interfacial Reaction above Liquidus

Si-Si hump is the main characteristics of hypereutectic Al-Si with super high Si content, but our DSC study in Fig.6 showed that SiCp/Al composite did not emerge the features of hypereutectic Al-Si melt after the thermal history in liquid metal X-ray diffraction and subsequent remelting. As illustrated in Fig.6, the comparison of onset and end temperature of Al-Si eutectic reaction and the changed liquidus temperature in the DSC heating and cooling trace suggested that the mean melt composition of the two kinds of SiCp/Al composites lies in the Al-Si hypoeutectic field. Both the results suggest that in the SiCp/Al composite melt exist a solute riched region with much more Si content.

Fig.6. DSC Trace for the remelting of SiCp/Al Composites (a) 10vol% (b) 40vol%

The Diffusion of Si above Liquidus

It is well-known that the liquid metal is featured by short-range-order and the cluster size, r_c , is the lower limit of the atom cluster, from the standpoint of the hard-sphere model in liquid metal structure theory, r_c is associated with the packing density η of the atom cluster, which is defined by $\eta = \frac{\pi}{6} n_0 \sigma^3$, where σ is atom diameter, the temperature dependence of packing density is expressed, in the first order approximation, by the following exponential function:

$$\eta(T) = A \exp(-QT) \quad (4)$$

where T is absolute temperature, the parameters A, based on experimental data for various metal, is the constant, Q is the diffusion active energy. Seen in Eqn.4, the temperature T increasing, the packing density η is lowering, and the size of SRO r_c is being small, but not linear. The size change in liquid Al implied that the fundamental features in the atomic distribution for the liquid are approximated more or less by a random mixture, and agreed

with the above equation. In SiCp/Al composite melt, with the temperature increasing, liquid Al is progressively becoming liquid Al-Si, and the theoretical calculation results showed that in Al-Si melt, the SRO is mainly Si-Si cluster because of the most strongest bond energy on Si-Si pair among Al-Al, Al-Si and Si-Si pairs[7]. The size change of SRO in SiCp/Al composite melt suggested that the diffusion of Si from the chemical reaction between SiC and molten Al can diffuse only after a given temperature or the concentration fluctuation of Si.

The Nature of the Distribution and Diffusion of Si above Liquidus

The emergence of Si-Si hump and the size change of SRO are attributed to the chemical reaction between SiC and molten and the variation of the viscosity in the composite melt. When solid particles are dispersed in a liquid metal, both the hydrodynamic interaction between liquid and the particles and non-hydrodynamic interaction between the particles themselves produce an increase in the apparent viscosity of composite melt, often by orders of magnitude than the unreinforced matrix alloy; on the other hand, additional variations in apparent viscosity may result from chemical reaction between the reinforcement and the matrix which alter the shape and volume fraction of the reinforcement. This effect has been shown to increase the apparent viscosity of Al-SiC particulate slurries[8], for 15vol% SiCp/A356 composites holding at 800 °C, resulting in a marked decrease in fluidity until, after 250 minutes, the composite will not flow because of the great reactivity between SiC particle and molten Al-7Si above 750 °C. Because the reactivity between SiC and pure Al is active greatly, the effect of the chemical reaction upon the viscosity in SiCp/pure Al is much more greater than that in SiC/A356.

For a particle (atom or molecular) with radius r_i , the relationship between the diffusion coefficient and the viscosity of the melt agree with the Stocks-Einstein Equation[9]:

$$D_i = \frac{\kappa_B T}{6\pi r_i \nu} \quad (5)$$

Where D_i represents the diffusion coefficient, ν represents viscosity of the melt, and κ_B is the Boltzman constant, T is the absolute temperature. when ν becomes larger, the diffusion coefficient D_i is more smaller, so the diffusion of atom i is more difficult. In fact, the effect of temperature change is more complex. In conventional liquid alloy, the viscosity decrease with increasing melt temperature, whereas the viscosity in SiC/Al composite decrease with increasing temperature and increasing SiC particle volume fraction due to the formation of Al_4C_3 .

The decrease of apparent viscosity results in the difficulties of atom (Si and Al) diffusion and heat convection, thus impeding the solute Si, Al from the chemical reaction redistribution, with the temperature increasing, the chemical reaction is more serious, the apparent viscosity is more higher, Si from the chemical reaction is accumulated in local zone around the SiC particles, and emerging Si-Si hump in pair radial distribution function $g(r)$. And as discussed above, only after a given temperature or some extent concentration fluctuation of Si, is the diffusion of Si possible.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present work, liquid metal x-ray diffraction, DSC have been used to investigate the melt structures in SiCp/Al composite above liquidus, the following results were obtained:

- (1). Si-Si hump emerging in Pair Radial Distribution Function suggested that Si riched region exist in the SiC/Al composite melt above liquidus, implying the distribution of Si are non-well -distributed above liquidus;
- (2).The size change of SRO in SiCp/Al composite indicated that the diffusion of Si from the

chemical reaction between SiC and molten Al is possible only after a given temperature or some extent concentration fluctuation of Si;

(3).The existence of Si-Si hump and the size change of SRO are attributed to the chemical reaction in SiCp/Al composite and the existence of reinforcing particles, high volume fraction plays more greater influence on the Si-Si hump and the size change of SRO than low volume fraction.

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